

CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS

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Annotation: *The main goal of this research article was to provide more information about creativity skills, which are among the most in-demand life and career skills in the twenty-first century, similar to creative thinking, problem-solving, or critical thinking ability, which is that the critically preliminary ability of global citizens in diverse societies.*

Key words: *Creativity, society, brainstorm, problem-based learning, actionable thinking, mind mapping, role playing.*

Аннотация: *Основная цель этой исследовательской статьи состояла в том, чтобы предоставить больше информации о творческих навыках, которые являются одними из самых востребованных жизненных и карьерных навыков в двадцать первом веке, подобно творческому мышлению, способности решать проблемы или критическому мышлению. , то есть критически предварительная способность граждан мира в различных обществах.*

Ключевые слова: *творчество, общество, мозговой штурм, проблемное обучение, активное мышление, интеллект-карта, ролевая игра.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqot maqolasining asosiy maqsadi 21-asrda eng ko'p talab qilinadigan hayotiy va martaba ko'nikmalaridan biri bo'lgan ijodiy fikrlash, muammolarni hal qilish yoki tanqidiy fikrlash kabi ijodiy qobiliyatlar haqida ko'proq ma'lumot berish edi. , ya'ni turli jamiyatlarda dunyo fuqarolarining tanqidiy dastlabki qobiliyati.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ijodkorlik, jamiyat, aqliy hujum, muammoli ta'lim, faol fikrlash, aql xaritasi, rolli o'yin.*

INTRODUCTION

Humanity and culture are progressing at an astonishing rate. We need to empower ourselves with the capacity to adapt to this tendency rather than resist it. We may accomplish tremendous success by confronting problems and reacting to them with a fresh perspective and self-assurance. The capacity to think creatively in both a digital and non-digital world has become an essential attribute of successful individuals today.

In the twenty-first century, information technology is quickly developing, and inventive thinking, problem-solving, or critical thinking capacity is the critically important skill of world individuals in diverse countries. "strength" in an era of strong worldwide competitiveness in the information industry. As a result, human resource development in recent years has emphasized the promotion of creative thinking capacity, as the "brain" will replace "strength" in the information economy era of strong worldwide competitiveness.

Lin, Cheng-Shih (2016). Sternberg and Lumbar (1996) define creativity as the ability to deal with a given challenge in authentic ways. This ability entails viewing a given circumstance or problem from several angles. Creativity goes beyond making something out of nothing since a new concept or thinking is frequently a variant form of an older notion or a mix of previously known or owned thoughts. Thus, creativity might be characterized as synthesizing and reframing earlier ideas (Bessus 1973). Creativity is a fundamental ability that is present in all facets of human existence and evolution (San 1985).

Torrance (1974) defines creativity as "being sensitive to problems, inadequacies, scarcity of information, nonexistent elements, and incompatibility; identifying challenges, seeking solutions, estimation and hypothesizing or modifying hypotheses in relation to inadequacies, selecting and trying one of the solutions, retrieval, and concluding accordingly" (cited by Aslan 2001). Looking for a solution to the question "What is creativity?" In the early 1960s, Repucci discovered 50-60 definitions in the literature (Parkhurst, 1999).

METHODOLOGY

Because the survey approach was used, this research is an integrated study. To discover relevant papers, we will conduct a systematic examination of the current literature on the Creative Thinking database, which will be augmented by an overview of the sources of relevant publications identified.

DISCUSSION

A definition of creativity is a means of seeing and solving issues from a unique viewpoint, eschewing conventional answers and thinking beyond the box. This creative process helps you to make new connections, face new obstacles, and seek unusual, original, and novel answers.

Many individuals, including Steve Jobs, believe that creative thinking approaches are based on experience and knowledge: Creativity is just concerned with things. When you ask a creative person how they created something, they often feel a bit bad since they did not actually do it; they simply saw something. After a time, it seemed plain to them. That is because they were able to link previous experiences and synthesize new ones. Furthermore, they were able to do so because they had more experiences or had thought more about their experiences than other individuals. Following that, we must recognize that creative thinking is a skill that must be trained first.

To begin thinking creatively, we must be willing to disrupt the patterns and old ways of thinking. The path you're on will make it easier for you to develop a completely different approach to a certain circumstance or issue. Starting with this strategy too young promises additional experience as you gain maturity and learn from many other cases. A method of viewing issues or circumstances from a new viewpoint, resulting in unconventional solutions (which may appear disconcerting at first). Creative thinking is frequently fostered by both an unstructured activity such as brainstorming and a controlled approach such as a heuristic program.

Furthermore, it can refer to perceiving something in a novel way. It's the epitome of "thinking outside the box." Often, creativity in this sense incorporates what is known as heuristic program, or the ability to detect patterns that aren't evident. In one famous

narrative, the fictional investigator Sherlock Holmes employs a heuristic algorithm when he discovers that a dog not barking indicates a murder case.

At its most basic, "creative" refers to the act of creating something that did not previously exist. The term "creativity" encompasses a wide variety of abilities. Creative abilities are required to change notions and perceptions. In most problem-solving descriptions, a phase termed "search for alternatives" is generally included. This implies that at this phase, ingenuity is essential. Creativity is misunderstood and difficult to demonstrate, yet there are beneficial approaches that anybody can master. Edward de Bono mentions creative strategies such as attention, challenge, alternatives, notions, and so on. E. De Bono (1993). Creativity should coexist with our other techniques of dealing with knowledge. A classic condition of affairs would be someone sitting down with the purposeful aim of producing a notion in a very specific region, then proceeding to employ an innovative thinking process systematically. Individuals that engage in creative thinking will go "sideways" to explore new perspectives, notions, and points of entry. To address the concerns, they will employ a variety of approaches, including provocations. To put forward alternative points of view, creative thinking has a lot to do with perception. The numerous points of view are not developed one from the other, but are generated individually. Ability, like perception, must be associated with exploration during this sense.

The capacity to generate an enormous amount of ideas from which to choose is referred to as idea fluency. According to research, the more ideas one has, the more likely one is to find a workable answer. Delaying concept evaluation during the idea generation process might help with idea fluency. Students might take notes, document their observations, and express their thoughts on difficulties during thanksgiving to aid in the process of concept fluency. Using certain times or locations where students prefer to initiate a debate in a creative way is a unique technique of encouraging concept fluency.

There are other issues that emerge and reveal themselves. Individuals develop distinct creative focuses. There is also an obvious creative necessity. These are

examples of creative foci that can arise. Whenever a creative focus has been established, it is frequently exposed to deliberate ability. This can be done by groups, individuals, or a combination of the two in an interactive discussion. It is common for the group with the priority or problem to organize its own deliberate ability session to address a mix of issues. The creative group may also be active in analyzing the ideas which encourage intentional creative thought. In such circumstances, the procedure is ongoing. If the "thinking" group differs from the "implementation" group, special attention must be devoted to idea transfer so that those expected to execute on the notion are brought in early enough to feel some ownership within the new ideas. It is essential to learn with creativity in order to be innovative at each step of discourse. A new definition of a thinking assignment is required. The structure for implementing the thought process must be innovative. The outcome of the thought process must be innovative. Finally, the assessment and implementation processes must be innovative. A framework of the equipment is required for creative thinking. Otherwise, students who are not visiting are put in a position where they must come up with fresh ideas. Regardless matter how effective the strategies are, if they are not implemented, they will be ineffective. (2008) (Awang and Rumley) They also suggest problem-based learning (PBL) as an instructional strategy that could encourage creative capabilities during the training process.

Picture 1: Actionable thinking.

You would prefer a backstory to help you comprehend things and circumstances. Knowledge enables creative thinkers to see the big picture, which is why they know so much about the world they create and are experts in what they do, as well as the land on which they build their knowledge.

Because the ability to adapt to changes and think outside the box are components of creative thinking, being flexible may be a distinguishing feature of creative thinkers. They appreciate change; they are not afraid to modify their way of labor; and they are adept at collaborating with others. Issues more effectively; earning respect; becoming an inventor; making a difference; and being more successful at work.

Methods of thinking creatively

Creative problem solving has become an essential ability for the twenty-first century as an inventive technique to exploring and evaluating ideas. Although some people appear to be more creative than others, this talent is something that is cultivated and strengthened via numerous strategies and practices.

Brainstorming is a strategy that involves thinking about something and writing down all of the ideas that occur to mind, no matter how ridiculous or irrelevant they may appear at first. In this sea of ideas, there will undoubtedly be one that stands out, one that is concrete and unique. Brainstorming, as a personal or medical practice, might be an excellent technique to build creativity and problem-solving skills. It fosters thinking in new ways and explores various possibilities that might be implemented in a given circumstance. The more choices that come to mind, the more likely it is that you will uncover fantastic ideas.

Mind mapping refers to the technique of connecting the dots. While brainstorming includes writing down all of the ideas that come to mind, mind mapping is about organizing your thoughts, thinking logically, using associations, detecting patterns, and establishing order. All of the ideas from brainstorming should be moved into mind mapping. This exercise uses both the left and right hemispheres of the brain and pushes you to consider the relationship between aspects and concepts. It also has a good impact on organizational abilities. Reframing is a fantastic exercise for fostering creative

thinking since it focuses on assessing the same circumstance or issue from a different viewpoint.

Role-playing: Using role-playing is a terrific approach to change your thoughts and investigate truth from a different angle. Because creative thinking encourages you to be open-minded, when using this method, you'll try and consider true from the perspective of someone else you wish to reframe your way of thinking to determine a distinct perspective of things, to vary the attitude and find new solutions that reassess your limits and overcome your personal variety of problem-solving. Taking on a substitute position motivates you to come up with answers that are unusual for you, but are just what you need for creative problem-solving.

Employers do not want to hire creative individuals merely because they are outstanding. They want innovative personnel that can assist them in resolving workplace difficulties. As a result, while looking for employment, emphasize your capacity to think creatively as well as use your ingenuity to solve crucial challenges.

CONCLUSION

We can conclude from this research that creativity skills are among the most sought-after life and work skills in the twenty-first century as an innovative approach to approaching and analyzing ideas, problem-solving, or critical thinking, and that this skill can be developed and improved using various techniques and practices.

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